

FINAL REPORT

SPOKE 1: MOUNTAIN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM

PROJECT NAME: Embodied Data Lab (EDALAB)

The Final Report relates to the scientific activities carried out and the results achieved within the project funded through the Young Researcher Call for Proposals: it must provide a comprehensive description of the project results, with specific reference to the project activities carried out, the progress made and the achievement of the milestones and targets set out in the approved project.

The Final Report is submitted by the PI (principal investigator) and is evaluated by the Scientific Committee, in accordance with the provisions of the aforementioned Call for Proposals.

The Final Report must underscore these aspects:

- the final objectives achieved and set out in the project submitted for evaluation, as well as any deviations from the established objectives and the reasons for such deviations;
- any deviations between the approved Economic and Financial Plan and the reported costs, that must be justified.

PROJECT DETAILS	
Spoke	6 – Tourism, culture and creative industries
PROJECT ACRONYM	EDALAB
PI – Principal Investigator - University	Dr. Maria Menendez-Blanco
Starting date:	04/10/24
Duration:	1 year and 27 days
Ending date:	31/10/2025
<i>Other participants - university</i>	naturmuseum Sütiroi, mischer'traxler studio

Annexes:

Possible annex	
Possible annex	

Date: 31/01/2026

PI signature: -----

1. Technical and scientific results of the project

1.1. Description of the final results achieved

Maximum two pages.

Images and diagrams may be attached at the end of the report. Indicate whether the expected results were achieved, explaining and quantifying any deviations.

Describe the expected and actual results of the project in qualitative terms.

As described in the project proposal, the Embodied Data Lab (embodieddata.labs.unibz.it) aimed to serve as a reference point locally, nationally, and internationally for leveraging data to develop sensitivities towards natural and cultural heritage through design and creativity. The case study in the Naturmuseum Südtirol exemplifies how this service addresses the pressing need of museums to digitise their archives and render them available through engaging narratives. This service contributes to the digitisation of scientific collections, which can be instrumental in other museums with physical archives but also to other institutions that want to use data to build narratives.

The actual results are well aligned with the initial proposal, and the impact of these results have exceeded our expectations. The outcomes are described with references to the tasks proposed in the original project workplan to demonstrate this alignment. For a visual overview, please see the end of this report.

During the project, the Embodied Data Lab established a collaboration with mischer'traxler studio (external service) and the Naturmuseum of Südtirol. Through an interdisciplinary approach, the museum's archive was taken as a starting point. Relevant data (i.e., plants, animals) were identified and collected through different techniques (**T1.1 Data Identification and collection**). These data were then used to create a narrative based on biodiversity change and shifting timeline paradigm, a known phenomenon that hinders awareness of biodiversity change¹. Species from the museum's archive were classified based on the expert knowledge of the museum's zoologist and a botanist into extincted, endangered, common, and new species and mapped onto a timeline. Interactive technologies were used to allow users explore different time scales that go beyond a human lifetime (**T1.2 Design of cultural and natural heritage narratives**).

A curated selection of the plants and animals in the archive were digitalised using AI techniques and physicalised using the Prototyping Lab at unibz (**T2.1 Artifact Digitalisation and Physicalisation**). Through discussions among the unibz and museum researchers and the designers from mischer'traxler, the interactive exhibition was conceptualised and developed. This exhibition is called "echoed nature", and it invites people to explore how biodiversity has changed in South Tyrol from 1850 to 2050 using the museum's archive data (**T2.2 Development of the interactive installation**). The exhibition was deployed at the Naturmuseum Südtirol, relying on the unibz infrastructure such as the wood workshops at the faculty of engineering (**T2.3 Exhibition deployment**). The exhibition opened on November 4th, 2025, with broad participation from local actors from the province, the university, and regional cultural institutions (e.g., MUSE, Naturpark Hauser).

The evaluation protocol assessed interaction qualities (e.g., usability, User experience, accessibility) and the impact that such an interactive exhibition has on museum visitors. A set of evaluation quality metrics were developed based on the framework for the experience of meaning in human-computer interaction² (**T1.3 Definition of Quality Metrics**). An evaluation of the installation was conducted from November 4th, 2025, to January 9th, 2026, which is the period that the installation was showed at the museum (**T.4 Evaluation of the**

¹ Mehrabi, Z., & Naidoo, R. (2022). Shifting baselines and biodiversity success stories. *Nature*, 601(7894), E17-E18.

² Mekler, E. D., & Hornbæk, K. (2019). A framework for the experience of meaning in human-computer interaction. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 1-15).

exhibition and service). The evaluation protocol and data gathering activities were approved by unibz Research Ethics Committee, and by unibz Privacy Office (**T3.2 Ethics, Data Management and Equal Opportunities**).

An effective and proactive project coordination, supported by Mountecos and unibz administrative staff, enabled a smooth deployment of the project, respecting the initial timeline (**T3.1 Project coordination and administration**). The project and exhibition have been/are being widely communicated through local, regional and international platforms with the support of unibz Press Office (**T3.3. Communication, dissemination, and exploitation**). A video of the project has been created and published as a collaboration between the project participants and unibz press office ([www.youtube.com/watch?v= I-E-C99vj8](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I-E-C99vj8)).

Leaflets of the exhibition have been distributed across the territory (e.g., libraries, cultural centers, unibz campuses). The exhibition has been published through the social media channels of unibz and the Naturmuseum. The local and regional media have shown interest in the project, with participation of local newspapers and TV media in the opening. The local newspaper Salto.bz conducted an interview to the project PI on the Embodied Data Lab Project. Local actors from, e.g., Eurac, naturparkhauser, geopark Bletterbach have participated in guided tours of the exhibition conducted by the project's PI and the botanist of the museum, expressing their interest in the project and future developments.

At the international level, the PI presented the project to the partners of the EU-funded project Sleeping Beauty - Nature meets Bauhaus (www.sleepingbeauty-project.eu), where the Naturmuseum is a partner. The interest triggered during this presentation led to featuring "echoed nature" in the EU-funded repository of "Interaction seeds" (www.interactionseeds.eu), where more than 50 'Seeds' have been selected as they demonstrate positive effects to co-create solutions or communicate Science to citizens, and that can be replicated by other stakeholders in new contexts and locations. Despite the limited project timeframe compared to academic timeframes, the project has been accepted to be presented in two academic venues: the SIM Conference organised by the Società Italiana di Marketing (10-12 September 2025, Napoli, Italy) and the 16th Biannual Conference of the Italian Special Interest Group on Human-Computer Interaction (SIGCHI) (6-10 October 2025, Salerno, Italy).

Articles about echoed nature/Embodied Data Lab published on the news:

- Usare i dati per creare narrazioni: <https://salto.bz/de/article/23122025/usare-i-dati-creare-narrazioni>
- unibz presenta la mostra Echoed Nature (<https://salto.bz/it/article/03112025/unibz-presenta-la-mostra-echoed-nature>)
- Biodiversität im Wandel: unibz präsentiert die Ausstellung Echoed Nature (<https://www.suedtirolnews.it/wirtschaft/biodiversitaet-im-wandel-unibz-praesentiert-die-ausstellung-echoed-nature>) (last access January, 14th 2026)
- "Echoed Nature": la biodiversità altoatesina raccontata (digitalmente) in 200 anni di cambiamenti (<https://www.altoadige.it/cultura-e-spettacoli/echoed-nature-la-biodiversitaet-C3%AO-altoatesina-raccontata-digitalmente-in-200-anni-di-cambiamenti-1.4214082>) (last access January, 14th 2026)
- unibz präsentiert Ausstellung über den Wandel der Biodiversität Ausstellungseröffnung am 4. November um 18.30 Uhr im Naturmuseum (<https://www.ladige.it/progetti/2025/10/31/unibz-praesentiert-ausstellung-uber-den-wandel-der-biodiversitaet-ausstellungseroefnung-am-4-november-um-18-30-uhr-im-naturmuseum-1.4214364>) (last access January, 14th 2026)

Scientific publications:

- Menéndez-Blanco M, Pretto N, Grillini G, Nicastro G, Condorelli F, Mischer K, Traxler T. "Assessing Meaning in Embodied Interactive Installations." (2025) In *Proceedings of the 16th Biannual Conference of the Italian SIGCHI Chapter (in press)*.

- Grillini G, Menéndez-Blanco M. Embodied Data Lab: Creating Interactive Experiences for Environmental and Cultural Awareness in Tourism, 2025, SIM Conference (Società Italiana di Marketing) *Marketing-Innovation Nexus – Past Insights for Future Challenges*, 10-12 September, Naples

Highlight the starting and final TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and the main KPI (Key Performance Indicator) achieved

Starting TRL - TRL 3: concept validated with analytic/design work and component-level prototypes (narrative, data identification, proof-of-concept digitalisation) but not yet demonstrated in an operational public setting.

Final TRL - TRL 8: complete system deployed and operated successfully in a real museum environment (public exhibition Nov 4, 2025–Jan 9, 2026), evaluated with approved evaluation protocols and shown to meet intended performance and user-experience goals.

Main KPI(s)

- Successful operational deployment: exhibition open to public for the full planned period (Nov 4, 2025–Jan 9, 2026).
- Visitor engagement and experience: usability/UX/accessibility metrics. Methodological contribution by developing an evaluation protocol for meaningful interactions with technologies in cultural heritage (evaluation completed per T1.3/T4).
- Reach and uptake: inclusion in the Interaction Seeds repository, regional/international presentations, media coverage, and active interest/collaboration from local institutions.

Describe the External Partners who collaborated, their contribution, and the possible synergies that may continue in the near future

- mischer'traxler studio (external service)
Contribution: Led conceptual and interaction design of the "echoed nature" installation, co-developed the exhibition with researchers, and developed and implemented the prototype. Near-term synergies: continued co-design of follow-up exhibitions, adaptation of the installation for other venues, joint proposals for funded public-engagement projects.
- Naturmuseum Südtirol (host partner)
Contribution: Provided archival collections, domain expertise (zoologist, botanist), venue for deployment, and local curatorial support for installation and guided tours. Near-term synergies: further digitisation of collections, extended or touring deployments of the installation, collaborative public programmes and visitor studies, joint proposals for funded public-engagement projects.

Future synergies: The Naturparkhäuser of South Tyrol have invited the "echoed nature" installation for a four-year touring program, a major endorsement of the Embodied Data Lab relevance and reach. The prototype will be hosted from 2026 to 2029 as temporary exhibition:

- **Naturparkhaus Texelgruppe (2026)**
- **Naturparkhaus Fanes-Sennes-Prags (2027)**
- **Naturparkhaus Schlern-Rosengarten (2028)**
- **Naturparkhaus Drei Zinnen (2029)**

As part of the Ufficio Natura, Ripartizione Natura, Paesaggio e Sviluppo del territorio from the Autonoma Bolzano Alto Adige, the Naturparkhäuser (naturparks.provinz.bz.it/de/naturparkhaeuser-und-infostellen) play a key role in South Tyrol by connecting visitors to local natural heritage, conservation practice, and regional education; hosting the installation across these sites significantly amplifies public impact, supports long-term data-driven engagement with biodiversity, and demonstrates the installation's robustness and adaptability for site-specific interpretation. We are currently formalising the lending agreement for the prototype with the unibz legal office.

1.2. Summary of deliverables

Name	Result ³	Links	TRL ⁴	Description and references
	[SCI] [PROD] [SERV] [PROC] [BUS] [DSG] [METH] [PO]	Link to Zenodo or BIA	[TRL4] [TRL5] [TRL6] [TRL7] [TRL8] [N.A.]	[Publication] [Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstrator or test] [Intellectual property management] [Patent submission] [Other]
echoed nature interactive exhibition	PROD		TRL8	Pilot, demonstrator or test

³ [SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory, etc.] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)]

⁴ [TRL4 - Technology validated in the laboratory] [TRL5 - Technology validated in the relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment] [TRL7 - Demonstration of the prototype system in an operational environment] [TRL8 - Complete and qualified system] [TRL9 - Real system tested in an operational environment] [Not applicable]

2. COMPLIANCE WITH CONDITIONALITIES AND ALL ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENTS RELATED TO THE PNRR MEASURES

2.1. DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code

Description of how the activities carried out comply with the DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code. In this regard, the reasons why the activities carried out do not cause significant harm to each of the environmental objectives are reported.

Environment	Has the DNSH principle been respected for the environmental objective? (Y/N) ⁵	Justifications:
1. Climate change mitigation	YES	The project's low-emissions activities (local fabrication, museum deployment) and focus on raising awareness of biodiversity change. Emissions from travel/production were limited and managed to the minimum possible
2. Climate change adaptation	YES	By communicating biodiversity shifts and timelines to the public and stakeholders, the project supports adaptive awareness and decision-making without causing harm
3. Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources	YES	The project's activities did not affect water or marine resources, so no significant harm was caused
4. Transition to a circular economy, including waste reduction and recycling	YES	Prototyping and deployment used existing university workshops and emphasised reusable assets. The touring of the echoed nature exhibition throughout four years reusing the hardware material optimises the resources used with respect to the impact. Standard disposal/recycling practices are applied when needed
5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution	YES	Project activities posed minimal pollution risk. Materials and fabrication were managed via institutional facilities and standard environmental practices
6. Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystem	YES	The project promotes biodiversity awareness, supports digitisation of natural collections for conservation research and public awareness, and does not harm habitats through its activities

⁵ If the activities carried out do not have an impact on the environmental objective, it is appropriate to answer "Yes", in case of "Not", enter the reasons in the "Justifications" column of the same table..

2.2. Consistency with the digital constraint

Max 500 characters

Describe how the activities carried out and the related expenses incurred contribute to the achievement of the digital constraint, thus promoting the digital transition and at the same time ensuring compliance with the contribution to the digital objective

The project's activities and related expenditures directly advance the digital transition by digitalising museum archives (digital scanning and AI-supported modelling), developing interactive software for the "echoed nature" installation, and investing in prototyping, deployment infrastructure, and approved data-management processes. These investments enabled reusable digital assets (digitised specimens, interactive installation).

Budgeted costs for the installation conceptualisation and development, and the formal processes supported by unibz (ethics approvals, privacy compliance, and storage) ensure the solution meets institutional and legal standards while maximising replicability.

Together, these activities both fulfill the project's digital objective—by creating a tested, deployable interactive exhibition—and comply with the contribution requirements through documented deliverables, approved ethics/privacy procedures, and demonstrable public deployment and dissemination

3. ECONOMICS RESULTS OF THE PROJECT

3.1. Project costs

Attach the final statement of costs incurred in connection with the project, indicating the type of cost incurred..

BUDGET			
	Final amount (€)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
Costs for specialist consultancy services	25620	21000 euros (35%)	the offer I received was a foreigner invoice from Austria that did not include IVA, as they need to pay it in their country. This issue was discussed at the time with the administration at Mountecos.
Costs for materials, supplies and similar products	26672,65	33000 euros (55%)	we did not need all the licenses for qualitative data analysis that were estimated in the original budget
Mission expenses	2746,62	6000 euros (10%)	1383,60 euros (T065175) Maria Menendez-Blanco spent to attend to the CHIItaly conference to present the project with an accepted poster. This amount was from the general iNEST project cost center. The reason for this was that the conference took place in October 2025, and the EDALAB project initially ended at the end of September. I needed to do the conference registration at the same moment the request for the project extension was sent. For the remaining amount, we did not need all the budget for presenting the project in conferences and events
Total	55039,27		

BUDGET			
	Final amount (€)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
RI -	29855,63	39543 (65%)	Some of the items that were bought as part of the SS (e.g., computer, software for data analysis) were also used for RI purposes. In addition, we relied on internal unibz infrastructure (wood workshop, prototyping lab, technical support) for the aspects of the project related to industrial development. This reliance lowered the costs.
SS -	25183,64	20457 (35%)	The SS activities were specially conducted in the initial months of the project, where we needed to purchase all potentially needed hardware/software to test whether they would be relevant for the development of the installation.
Total	55039,27		

4. SUMMARY OF TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC CHANGES TO THE PROJECT (IF ANY)

Summarise the technical and financial changes that have been made to the project. Please note that, according to the call for proposals, changes must not substantially alter the objectives, results and impact of the initial project and must not lead to an increase in total expenditure. Please also specify whether the changes have an impact on the balance between the different types of expenditure.

The project has not suffered from major technical or financial changes in comparison with the initial proposal. All the objectives have been successfully met and the impact in the territory has exceeded the initial expectations, as described in detailed with respect to the work packages and tasks in the original proposal. The total expenditure did not increase with respect to the initial request. The main budget change has been in respect to the external service (from 21k to 25620). This change has not been due to change in the planning of the project but a tax situation (the company that was selected for the external service is based in Austria).

Figure 1 - Leaflet of the exhibition (front)

Crediti del progetto

Ricercatrice principale:
María Menéndez-Blanco / Faculty of Engineering, unibz
Direzione artistica e design espositivo:
Katharina Mischer und Thomas Traxler / mischer'traxler studio
Consulenza scientifica, Selezione e preparazione delle collezioni:
Petra Kranebitter, Thomas Wilhelm / Museo di Scienze Naturali dell'Alto Adige
Installazione interattiva:
mischer'traxler studio with Marlen Jachek, Simon Laburda (DKIA)
Valutazione scientifica:
María Menéndez-Blanco, Giulia Grillini, Niccolò Pretto / unibz
3D scanning e AR:
Giuseppe Nicastro, Francesca Condorelli / unibz
Riprese e montaggio:
Matteo Vegetti / unibz
Con il sostegno di:
iNEST, unibz, Museo di Scienze Naturali dell'Alto Adige
Finanziato da:
iNEST project (Interconnected North-East Innovation Ecosystem) funded by the European Union Next-GenerationEU, Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR) Missione 4 Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 D.D. 1058 23/06/2022, ECS 00000043, Spoke6, Bando Young Researcher, CUP I43C22000250006

unibz team: María Menéndez-Blanco (PI), Giulia Grillini (Co-PI), Giuseppe Nicastro, Niccolò Pretto, Francesca Condorelli, Stefania Denise Escobar, Chiara Massaccesi, Eliana Saracino, Andrea Facchetti

embodieddata.labs.unibz.it

mischertraxler.com

Figure 2 - Leaflet of the exhibition (back)

Figure 3 - Preview of the video of the make over and interactive installation available at [www.youtube.com/watch?v= I-E-C99vj8](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I-E-C99vj8)

Figure 4 - mischer'traxler and the botanist of the museum working at the archive

Figure 5 - an example of a plant from the museum archive

Figure 6 - Physicalisation of the digital models of extinct plants at the Prototyping Lab (Fac. Engineering)

Figure 7 - Research work at the museums archive with the zoologist

Figure 8 - Digitalisation of the archive by mischer'traxler

Figure 9 - Digitalisation of fragile specimens using scanning by unibz researchers

Figure 10 - Example of a digitalised extincted bird from the museum's archive

Figure 11 - Augmented Reality (AR) application to interact with extincted species from the archive

Figure 12 - Snapshot of the interactive installation, visitors see their silhouette filled with plants and animals from the museum's archive

Figure 13 - Silhouette from 1850, 1950 and 2050 made with plants and animals from the archive

Figure 14 - Data visualisation showing an overview of biodiversity change in South Tyrol from 1850 to 2050

Figure 15 - Part of the exhibition dedicated to neobiota from the museum's archive

Figure 16 - AR application in the exhibition dedicated to extincted species

Oggi sono stato/a al Museo di Scienze Naturali di Bolzano e ho visto la mostra interattiva "Echoed Nature". La prima cosa che ho provato quando ho visto la mia sagoma composta da elementi naturali è stata...

Se potessi parlare con me stesso/a nel futuro, mi chiederei come la visita alla mostra ha influenzato...

Compilando questa cartolina, acconsente a essere contattato dal nostro team di ricerca tra tre mesi per alcune domande sulla sua esperienza. Per ulteriori informazioni sulla raccolta dei dati e sulla privacy, visitare il sito web dell'Embodied Data Lab. Saremmo felici di ricevere i suoi commenti o domande—non esiti a scriverci a: maria.menendezblanco@unibz.it

Sono d'accordo Non sono d'accordo

data _____

email _____

età
 18-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65+

Quale opzione descrive meglio dove sei nato/a?
 Urbano Rurale Suburbano Altro (specificare)
.....

Quale opzione descrive meglio dove vivi adesso?
 Urbano Rurale Suburbano Altro (specificare)
.....

Figure 17 - example of postcard for data collection from visitors